

NOTES

TABLE 1

Composition (mole %)	Platinum concentration (wt. %)					Temperature (°C)			
	Temp. = 300° ; Contact time = 0.79 hr					Contact time = 0.79 hr ; Catalyst C			
	0.10	0.30	0.60	0.90	1.40	200	250	300	350
3-Carene unchanged	11.0	10.0	10.0	13.0	14.0	15.0	13.0	10.0	4.0
Menthadienes	37.0	28.0	3.0	10.0	26.0	6.4	7.0	3.0	1.0
Cymenes	44.0	53.0	75.0	67.0	52.0	60.0	63.0	75.0	83.0
Menthanes and menthenes	8.0	9.0	12.0	10.0	8.0	18.6	17.0	12.0	10.0

TABLE 2

	Cesium concentration (wt. %)				Hydrofluoric acid concentration (wt. %)		
	Contact time = 0.79 hr ; Catalyst C ; Temp. = 300°				Contact time = 0.79 hr ; Catalyst C ; Temp. = 300°		
	0	0.5	1.0	1.5	0	5	10
3-Carene unchanged	10.0	6.0	7.0	7.0	10.0	9.0	10.0
Menthadienes	3.0	6.0	15.0	18.0	3.0	29.0	33.0
Cymenes	75.0	78.3	70.0	69.0	75.0	56.0	52.0
Menthanes and menthenes	12.0	10.0	8.0	6.0	12.0	5.0	5.0

The effect of temperature on the rate of reaction as well as on the distribution of products is included in Table 1. The conversion of 3-carene increases with increasing temperature. The proportion of the intermediates, viz., the menthadienes, falls rapidly due to their further conversion to cymenes, menthanes and menthenes. Increase of temperature decreases the concentration of menthanes and menthenes also indicating the onset of their excessive dehydrogenation to cymenes, which appears to outweigh their formation.

The effect of cesium and fluoride ions on the reaction of 3-carene is given in Table 2. Addition of cesium brings about a small reduction in the conversion of 3-carene while hydrofluoric acid does not affect it. The increasing concentration of menthadienes with increasing cesium and fluoride ions is attributed to the reduction of the metal surface through blocking by these ions. As a result, the dehydrogenation and disproportionation activities of the catalyst diminish. To confirm this further, the dehydrogenation of cyclohexane and dehydrogenation and disproportionation of cyclohexene have been carried out over these modified catalysts. Here too, the reaction decreased with increasing concentrations of cesium and fluoride ions¹⁰.

Of the Cs⁺ and F⁻ ions, the latter decreases the formation of cymenes to a greater extent. Fluoride ions have been found to enhance the strength of acid sites¹². These strong sites may isomerise the six membered menthadienes to five membered alkyl cyclopentadienes as reported by Pines *et al.*¹³. These alkyl cyclopentadienes may polymerise over the strong acid sites leading to the formation of carbonaceous material which deposits over the active sites reducing the activity of the catalyst. The strong tendency of the C₅ ring compounds to polymerise when in contact with acid sites is well known¹⁴.

Cesium ions in low concentrations exhibit a promoting effect (Table 2), which lies in their ability to neutralise the strong acid sites that will otherwise catalyse the undesired side reactions as described earlier.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. G. S. Laddha, Director, for facilities.

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Synthesis of a Possible Metabolite of Trifluoperazine 2-Trifluoromethyl-7-Hydroxy-8-Methoxy-10-[3-(4-Methyl-1-Piperazinyl)-Propyl]-Phenothiazine-5-Oxide and Related Compounds

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Manuscript received 25 August 1980, revised 1 March 1983, accepted 19 July 1983.

TRIFLUOPERAZINE^{1,2}, one of the most important drug in the treatment of mental illness has been in use for the last two decades. This class of compounds possess therapeutic properties as tranquillizers, antiemetics, antihistaminics, spasmolytic and antishock agents. This initiated an interest

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Scheme 1

to elucidate the therapeutic mechanism of the drug. In this note we report the synthesis of the oxidation product of 7,8-disubstituted analogue of 2-trifluoromethyl phenothiazine by various methods. The synthesis of some of the key intermediates viz., 2-trifluoromethyl-7-isopropoxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine (**I**), 2-trifluoromethyl-7-isopropoxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine dioxalate (**II**) and 2-trifluoromethyl-7-isopropoxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine-5-oxide dioxalate (**III**) have also been described.

The synthesis of 2-trifluoromethyl-7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine-5-oxide (**V**) involves base-catalysed (NaH) condensation of 2-trifluoromethyl-7-isopropoxy-8-methoxy phenothiazine⁸ with 1-(3-chloropropyl)-4-methyl piperazine⁴ to give **I**. The stable dioxalate of **I** is oxidised with 30% H₂O₂ and the resulting product (**III**) is hydrolysed to give **IV**. The latter is treated with alc. HCl to give the desired product (**V**) which was characterised as its stable dioxalate salt (**VI**).

Synthesis of **VI** was also carried out by direct oxidation of 2-trifluoromethyl-7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine dioxalate with perbenzoic acid at room temperature. The identity of the products obtained by the two methods was confirmed by m.m.p.

Experimental

2-Trifluoromethyl-7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine-5-oxide (V): A mixture of 2-trifluoromethyl-7-isopropoxy-8-methoxy phenothiazine (4.97 g), dry dimethylsulphoxide (250 ml), sodium hydride (2.04 g; 20% dispersion in mineral oil) was stirred at room temp. for 2 hr and then a solution of 1-(3-chloropropyl)-4-methyl-piperazine (3.87 g) in dry dimethylsulphoxide (25 ml) was added drop wise. The mixture was heated under reflux for 5 hr, cooled and poured into water, extracted with ether, acidified with 10% HCl and basified with 10% NaOH. The pale yellow solution was extracted with ether, dried, decolourised and concentrated to give 2-trifluoromethyl-7-isopropoxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine (**I**) as yellow oil. The oil was converted into its stable dioxalate (**II**). A mixture of **II** (3.37 g), ethanol (30 ml), water (10 ml), 30% H₂O₂ (0.51 g) was heated under reflux for 7 hr. The solvent was removed and the pale yellow residue was washed with ethanol and then with ether to give 2-trifluoromethyl-7-isopropoxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine-5-oxide dioxalate (**III**). The latter was hydrolysed with Na₂CO₃ to give 2-trifluoromethyl-7-isopropoxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine-5-oxide (**IV**) as a yellow crystalline product. A solution of **IV** (12.7 g) in conc. HCl and ethanol (15 ml) was heated under reflux for 1 hr. The resulting brown mixture was cooled, filtered,

TABLE 1

Sl.No.	Phenothiazine derivative	Yield %	m.p. °C	Colour	Formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		
						C	H	N
1.	2-Trifluoromethyl-7-isopropoxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine	75	Characterized as oil	Yellow	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ F ₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	60.50 (60.60)	6.40 (6.46)	8.41 (8.48)
2.	2-Trifluoromethyl-7-isopropoxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine dioxalate	80	215	White	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ F ₃ N ₂ O ₁₀ S	51.45 (51.55)	5.30 (5.37)	6.12 (6.22)
3.	2-Trifluoromethyl-7-isopropoxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine-5-oxide dioxalate	80	202	White	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ F ₃ N ₂ O ₁₁ S	50.30 (50.36)	5.16 (5.20)	6.01 (6.07)
4.	2-Trifluoromethyl-7-isopropoxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine-5-oxide	60	200	White	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ F ₃ N ₂ O ₈ S	46.53 (46.63)	6.26 (6.26)	8.15 (8.21)
5.	2-Trifluoromethyl-7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine-5-oxide	50	192	Light yellow	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ F ₃ N ₂ O ₈ S	56.21 (56.28)	5.49 (5.54)	8.87 (8.95)
6.	2-Trifluoromethyl-7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine-5-oxide dioxalate	70	191-193 (Foaming with decomp.)	White	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ F ₃ N ₂ O ₁₁ S	48.00 (48.07)	4.58 (4.62)	6.40 (6.46)

poured into water and adjusted to pH 8 with 10% NaOH. The residue was separated and extracted with ether, decolourised and recrystallised to give V as white crystals. V was converted into its dioxalate salt (VI).

Preparation of 2-trifluoromethyl-7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine-5-oxide dioxalate (VI) with perbenzoic acid: A mixture of 2-trifluoromethyl-7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-propyl]-phenothiazine dioxalate (1.89 g), CHCl₃-EtOH mixture (1:1) (100 ml), perbenzoic acid (10 ml) was stirred at room temp for 40 min and filtered. The resulting precipitate was washed with NaHCO₃ soln. (2%) and crystallized from hot EtOH to give yellow crystals.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship to one of them (M.A.).

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Synthesis of 6,7-Dimethoxy-3',4'-Methylenedioxyflavone (Milletenin-C)

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Manuscript received 10 September 1982, accepted 19 July 1983

MILLETENIN-C was isolated as a sticky but tlc pure compound from the leaf extract of *Millettia ovalifolia* along with two other flavonoids, milletenin-A and milletenin-B by Khan and Zaman¹. Its structure as 6,7-dimethoxy-3',4'-methylenedioxyflavone (I) was based on its identity only on tlc with the dehydrogenation product of a natural flavanone, milletenin-A (II). However, no data except m.p. was reported even for the dehydrogenation product.

Jain *et al*² proposed a synthesis for milletenin-C which consists of the oxidation of 2'-hydroxy-4',5'-dimethoxy-3,4-methylenedioxychalkone (III) with selenium dioxide. This communication reports the synthesis of milletenin-C thereby confirming its proposed structure (I). The synthesis was achieved by using 2-(3',4'-methylenedioxy)benzoyloxy-4,5-dimethoxyacetophenone (V) obtained by the esterification of 2-hydroxy-4,5-dimethoxyacetophenone (IV) with 3,4-methylenedioxybenzoyl chloride in presence of pyridine. The ester (V) when treated with KOH in pyridine underwent Baker-Venkataraman migration to give 2-hydroxy-4,5-dimethoxy-3',4'-methy-

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